

EFFECT OF INTERFACIAL REACTION ON THE FRACTURE BEHAVIOR OF $Al_{18}B_4O_{33}w/Al$ COMPOSITE AFTER T6 TREATMENT

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ABSTRACT

The interfacial reaction in the $Al_{18}B_4O_{33}w/AC8A$ Al composite was studied using TEM analysis, and the tensile fracture behavior was investigated by SEM dynamic observation. The result indicate that the interfacial reaction product is $MgAl_2O_4$. Because of interfacial reaction, the Mg content near by the whisker is lower than that far from the whisker. So the precipitation phase (Mg-rich phase) can not form near the whisker, i.e, a PFZ (precipitate free zone) exists near by the whisker. PFZ has a great effect on the fracture process of the composite.

INTRODUCTION

The alumina borate whisker ($Al_{18}B_4O_{33}w$, [AIBO]w)reinforced aluminum composite has been subjected to intensive investigation because of its lower price^[1-8]. Although there are many papers are about the interfacial reaction, the study on the effect of the interfacial reaction on the fracture behavior is limited. It is well known that aging treatment is an important harding method for the aluminum alloy matrix composite^[7,9]. Because the interfacial reaction in [AIBO]w/AC8A Al composite is alos concern with Mg atoms of the matrix alloy, and precipitation in [AIBO]w/AC8A Al composite is affected by the interfacial reaction greatly^[8].

In this study, the interfacial reaction and its effect on fracture behavior of [AIBO]w/AC8A Al composite after T6 treatment were studied.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

[AIBO]w/AC8A Al composite was prepared by squeeze casting method, the volume fraction of the whisker is 0.25. The composition of AC8A alloy is Si: 12.0 wt%, Cu: 1.0 wt%, Mg: 1.0 wt%, Ni : 1.0wt% and Al: 85.0 wt%. The specimens are solutionized at 500 °C for 5h then quenched into water with 80 °C, then aged at 205°C.

The interfacial reaction was investigated by TEM observation with CM-12 type transmission microscopy. The specimens for TEM observation were prepared by standard ion-thinning method.

The fracture process of the composites after T6 treatment was studied by SEM in-situ observation and fractographs were also investigated.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Interfacial reaction

The TEM photographs of the composite after solution treatment are shown in Fig. 1, the morphology of the interface (Fig. 1-a) shows that there exists obvious interfacial reaction between the whisker and the AC8A alloy, and the select area electron diffraction pattern (SAED) as shown in Fig. 1-b indicated that the interfacial reaction product is $MgAl_2O_4$ with spinal structure^[5-8].

Fig. 1 TEM photographs of the interface in the [AlBO]w/AC8A Al composite, (a) morphology of the interface, (b) SAED pattern of the interface

B. Microstructure of the aged composite

The TEM microstructure of the peak aged and over aged composite are shown in Fig. 2(a) and (b) respectively, the precipitation phase can be found both in the area which is near by the whisker but the area which is far from the whisker. But in over aged composite the precipitation phase can be seen only in the area far from the whisker. Hu et al^[6] indicated that the interfacial reaction can take place during the solution treatment, the interfacial reaction consumes the Mg content in the area which is near by the whisker, so the precipitate phase (β - Mg_2Si phase) can not form in this area in the over aged composite, which results in the precipitation free zone (PFZ) is formed near by the whisker.

C. Strength of the composite and AC8A alloy

The ultimate tensile strength (UTS) of the composite and the AC8A alloy shown in Fig. 3, after peak aging, the UTS of the composite decrease with the aging time more quickly than that of the AC8A alloy. This phenomena is related with the formation of PFZ in over aged composite.

Fig. 2 TEM microstructure of the peak aged composite (a) and over aged composite (b)

Fig. 3 Relationship between the UTS of the composite and AC8A alloy and aging time

D. In-situ observation of the fracture process of the composite

The SEM images of the crack initiation are shown in Fig.4, it can be seen that the probability of the cracks initiate near by the whisker in the over aged composite is bigger than that in the under and peak aged composite. From above study, it can be suggested that the PFZ in the over aged composite is a relative softening area, and the crack will initiate in the PFZ easily. In under aged and peak aged composite the precipitation distribution is relatively random, or there no obvious PFZ can be formed, so the cracks can initiate in the every area of the matrix or by the fracture and the whisker because of good bonding between the whisker and the matrix.

Fig. 4 SEM images of the crack initiation of the composite
(a) under aged , (b) peak aged , (c) over aged .

The SEM images of the crack propagation are shown in Fig.5, in the over aged composite many crack propagate along the whisker, that is to say, the crack propagation alone is the main mechanism of the fracture for the over aged composite, which is due to the PFZ formation. But, in under or peak aged composite the cracks can propagate in the matrix or along interface, because of no obvious PFZ formation.

Fig. 5 SEM images of crack propagation of the composite ,
(a) under aged , (b) peak aged , (c) over aged

The fractographs of the composite are shown in Fig.6, from the Fig.6, it can be found that the small dimple is the main character for the peak aged composite, this means that the bonding strength of the interface is quite good. In over aged composite, it can be found that there exist many coarse cracks because of the fracture of the PFZ, so the UTS of the over aged composite decreases more quickly than that AC8A alloy (see Fig.3).

From above study, it can be concluded that it is very important to control the aging condition for optimize the strength of the [AlBO]w/Al composite.

Fig. 6 Fractographs of the composite, (a) peak aged and (b) over aged

CONCLUSIONS

1. there exists interfacial reaction in [AlBO]w/AC8A Al composite, the product of the interfacial reaction is $MgAl_2O_4$
2. the interfacial reaction consumes the Mg content in the matrix of the composite, and results in the formation of PFZ in the over aged composite.
3. the crack initiates and propagates along PFZ near by the whisker mainly, so the UTS of the over aged composite decrease with the aging time.

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